

Highly active multimetallic nano alloys embedded in conducting polymer: Implementation in fuel cells and photocatalysis

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Abstract

Conducting polymer nanostructures has been recognized as photocatalysts, a promising breakthrough in photocatalysis and other energy conversion application, such as fuel cell and battery in the near future (1, 2). A facile method has been developed for the synthesis of Pd, and Pt nanoparticles (NPs) based multimetallic nanoalloys incorporated on polypyrrole (Ppy) nanofibers by colloidal radiolytic technique (3, 4). Metal nanoparticle is uniformly deposited on polypyrrole nanofibers, showing a significantly high electrocatalytic activity and durability compared with the Pd/C catalyst for electrooxidation of methanol or ethanol. The ultrasmall Pd₃₀Pt₂₉Au₄₁/Ppy nanohybrids (~8 nm) exhibit an excellent electrocatalytic activity which is ~5.5 times higher than monometallic counter parts (12 A per mg Pd, 5 times higher activity compared to Pd/C catalyst). An efficient light harvesting hybrid nanostructures based on Poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene) (PEDOT) nanofibers and gold nanoparticles (Au NPs) was prepared successfully via an one pot colloidal synthetic route. The plasmonic Au NPs (~6 nm) are synergistically integrated on the conductive polymer nanofibers as evident from microscopic techniques. The Au/Ppy nanohybrids (NHs) demonstrate superior photocatalytic activity for organic pollutant degradation under visible light irradiation which is ~5.6 times higher than bare polymer.

Keywords: Conducting polymer nanostructures, Nanohybrids, Metal nanoparticles, Visible light active photocatalyst, H₂ generation

References:

1. S. Ghosh et al. *Nat. Mater.*, 14 (2015), 505
2. S. Ghosh et al. *Nanoscale*, 8 (2016), 6921
3. S. Ghosh et al. *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces*, 9 (2017) 33775
4. S. Ghosh et al. *Sustainable Energy & Fuels*, 1(2017) 1148